

CONTENT OF METHODS OF TEACHING MUSIC IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article makes scientific observations about the content of the methodology of teaching music in higher educational institutions, the form, method, method, technology and means of its teaching, as well as the pedagogical conditions for their use.*

Keywords: *music, method, content, form, method, instrument, technology, methodology, teaching technologies, mechanism, conditions, pedagogy.*

Introduction. Musical perception, musical intonation, students' perfect assimilation of auditory, singing and music-theoretical knowledge, communicative capabilities of music, artistic and aesthetic influence in organizing the content of music teaching methods in the higher education system in world music education and research institutes. A number of scientific- research work on the introduction of interactive technologies in the development of its features. At the same time, it is necessary to optimally direct the musical interests of future music students, develop their creative abilities in relation to singing activities, develop artistic imagination and thinking, introduce information technologies into music education, ensure the harmony of theory and practice in teaching. Particular attention is paid to research and experimental - design activities aimed at issues such as support.

In this regard, in connection with the development of information technology in our Republic, special attention is paid to improving the methodology of teaching music in higher educational institutions. In order to improve the methods, methods and technologies of teaching music theoretical subjects to music education students, a number of scientific, theoretical and scientific and practical works are carried out [2]. A regulatory framework has been created for the implementation of new forms of organizing educational activities, improving the quality and efficiency of education, improving art education in accordance with modern social needs, and the material and technical base is developing. The issue of in-depth teaching of musical-theoretical Vajroism and the creation of an effective mechanism for introducing scientific and innovative achievements into practice was raised as a priority task. This expands the possibilities for improving music teaching methods based on an innovative approach to studying music teaching methods for undergraduate music education students.

Main part. Scientific methods of teaching music are carried out in the third and fourth years of undergraduate studies in the field of pedagogy of the higher education system. The purpose of teaching this subject is not only to deepen the knowledge of students and prepare them to become qualified teachers in their specialty, but also to see that they must master the methods and tools to be able to put them into practice, both productively and in practical activities. and musical literacy.

The modern system of music education is characterized by significant innovative changes and reflects innovative approaches to educational problems. Currently, the professional training of future music teachers remains one of the pressing issues. Considering the need for professional training of a music teacher, today it has become clear that in order to implement it, it is more effective to introduce innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process. Enriching

pedagogical knowledge with innovative technologies is becoming a necessity. Higher education systems should select widely used music teaching technologies. A wide circle of domestic and foreign scientists M.V. Clarin, Z.A. Litova, B.T. Likhachev, A.S. Petelin, G.K. Selevko, V.A. Slastenin, F.F. Yanushkevich, I.B. Gorbunova, D. Lebrer, R. Hammer, D. Kellner, E. Frolova, T. Ryabova, O. Rogach, local scientists N. Kiyamov, Sh. Mustafoev, K. Panjiev, U. Yuldoshev and a number of other scientists from the discussion in carried out their research. They promoted the application of educational technologies in higher education institutions and their effective use [2].

The purpose of the study is to determine ways to effectively use innovative pedagogical technologies in music education. Thus, the methods and techniques proposed by music pedagogy researchers are dominated by past pedagogical practices and they believe they should be used today. It is important to look for new alternative ways of learning to equip graduates with the skills and competencies to adapt to the new changing environment. In this regard, V.P. Bospalko, I.I. Markhel, K. Selevko and others are notable for the fact that they collected fundamental materials for a deeper understanding of the real and preliminary determination of the results of educational activities of undergraduate students [4]. In this regard, various approaches to the classification of innovative technologies have often been studied, analyzed and synthesized.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, music education involves increasing the target preparedness of students, youth and students on the basis of a specific program established with the help of a teacher. In the music education system of our country, issues of training, education and professional development of personnel in the field of music are a thing of the distant past. The sphere of music is largely connected with the creativity and life of our people. At the same time, folk pedagogy, which is the basis of music education, is becoming increasingly important every day. Uzbek folk songs of our people, statuses and epics, which form the heart of our classical music, have established themselves as an important factor in educating our youth in the spirit of patriotism, hard work and humanity [2].

Among the enormous reforms taking place in the social life of our people, a number of important changes took place in the system of higher music education at the end of the twentieth century. The organization of music clubs, which have become widespread in preschool and school educational institutions, as well as extracurricular children's music and art schools, secondary schools, as well as our small research in the pedagogical sphere of the higher education system, which is considered The main subject of music education in the direction of undergraduate education, a large attention is paid to the issues of improving the methodology of teaching music sciences, creating its educational and methodological support [1].

In this regard, starting from 2018, existing higher education organizations in our Republic will provide musical instruments in the field of music education in the field of pedagogy, as well as music teachers in the field of pedagogy and local characteristics of our country. Republic The training of specialists in the professions of performing and vocal singing has begun. To confirm our opinion, we can cite the example of pedagogical institutes and universities operating in our republics and opening new ones.

As in all other areas, our country looks with interest at its national musical heritage, which has been banned for many years in the history of our pedagogy since independence. This spiritual heritage of ours has determined the ways of using music pedagogy in educating the younger generation. Thoughts rich in content began to be used in the process of musical education and upbringing. Gradually, music education, which is our spiritual heritage, began to be widely used

in the creation of teaching aids, textbooks and teaching aids in accordance with new laws and programs. Our rich history of music serves as the basis for the development of music education today.

The content, goals and objectives of music education change and improve as a result of the rich experience accumulated over time. Currently, the important directions of human activity are the goals set in this activity, that is, the methodology and technology of music education, based on a systemic, that is, modular training system, are being further developed. Today, these new teaching technologies serve to more fully reveal the content and essence of music education.

If we look at the word “methodology” in the content of music education. The word “Methodology” comes from the Greek language and means “way”, “method”, “way of research”, “method of knowledge” and is considered one of the important parts of education. Their generalization is called methods of music education. Music teaching methodology studies the rules of teaching. This determines modern methods used in the education and upbringing of the younger generation. Methodology refers to the content of the teacher's experience and methods of working with students in the teaching and learning process.

If we pay attention to the dependence of the methodology on the aspect of training. It is the process of demonstrating to others by example the positive aspects of the lessons and intellectual potential that each person has acquired throughout his life.

Therefore, the method of education has a clear goal, and on the basis of traditions and values formed in socio-historical experience, it is necessary to educate the ever-growing young generation as a mature personality, both physically and morally, its behavior is a process of broad development of worldview and intellect.

Qualified and experienced professors and teachers, methodologists in connection with the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4884 dated November 6, 2020 “On additional measures to further improve the education system” and representatives in this area prepared the “Concept for ensuring the integrity of music education in systems of preschool, general secondary, vocational and higher education.” The content of this concept notes that each link in the education sector is considered the main guiding document in the development of state educational standards and subject programs. After this, the goals and objectives of preparing a complex of “Continuing Education Programs” of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of music were determined. In addition, in the process of improving scientific programs, the experience of Russia, England, Bulgaria, Japan, South Korea and Finland was studied. When analyzing general secondary education curricula with the help of UNICEF, the programs of Japan, Korea, Hong Kong and Singapore were studied, as well as the experience of Cambridge with presidential schools.

Vocational education programs adopted by the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCO) of the UNESCO organization dated May 15, 2020 “On measures to organize the activities of the national system for the development of professional qualifications, knowledge and skills in the Republic of Uzbekistan” 287, approved decision. This document defined “Skills and abilities”, “Knowledge”, “Competencies”, “Ways to achieve the appropriate level of qualifications” in accordance with 8 qualification levels.

Achieving high results in the field of music education, correctly assessing activities and being recognized by others is one of the most important tasks of music education methodology.

To accomplish such a task, a music teacher needs to work tirelessly on himself. The reason for this is that music education and training develop in harmony with each other.

The content of modern music education is defined as an educationally oriented and pedagogically sound system of musical knowledge, skills and abilities, acting in conjunction with the experience of musical and creative activity and a person's emotional and moral attitude to reality. The elements of the content of music education are: musical material - the experience of a person's emotional and moral attitude to the surrounding reality; musical knowledge; musical abilities. In the process of musical education, all elements are interconnected and implemented in unity [4].

The understanding of music as an art form is based on two levels of knowledge. These are: generalized basic knowledge that helps to form a comprehensive understanding of the art of music;

personal knowledge about music - elements of expressiveness of musical speech (dynamics, tempo, rhythm, etc.), biographical information about composers and performers, the history of the creation of a musical work.

Our observations and research have shown that the content of music education may include:

The content of any subject is in one way or another connected with other subjects. Interdisciplinary connections, first of all, mutual consistency of the content of education of different academic subjects, optimal consideration of educational tasks determined by the general goals of education and the specifics of each academic subject, relate to the construction and selection of material determined.

In the content of musical science, works related to other types of art are considered from the point of view of their artistic properties, aesthetic value and the subject of the lesson.

Music is an important factor in ensuring a person's education and musical knowledge, developing his skills and abilities, discovering new creative abilities, and developing comprehension of knowledge through logical thinking. Music education is a process of creative activity that can guide students in developing cognitive abilities and actions. This process is a process of creative activity that helps students to be creative, understand society and nature, and find their place in the future [5]. In music education, a person studying this science follows the path of knowledge in order to know what he does not know, clarify the unclear and gain a deeper mastery of the science. The student acquires performing abilities and skills and develops them increasingly.

The main task of a qualified teacher when creating creative activities is to teach students to work independently and guide them accordingly. Therefore, one of the important tasks is the

ability to identify students' interests and organize musical performance that arouses their inner interest [6].

It is advisable to use various pedagogical technologies to attract the main attention of students in music theory lessons. A teacher in a modern education system should provide music education to such students who should not face difficulties in learning the subject, but should learn it through interest [3].

A future music teacher must be able to demonstrate all his skills while working with students. The creative activity of the teacher contributes to the growth of students' thinking, consolidation of memory, correct assessment of surrounding events and events and, of course, conscious perception of music.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that the main tasks of music education are the correct organization of independent learning and paying attention to the issues of cultivating the worldview and thinking of students. To do this, students need to be provided with a creative environment and given the knowledge necessary to become a professional in their field. In this situation, the teacher needs to teach musical knowledge step by step and give the right instructions for independent practice at home.

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